

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DESIGN OF NONLINEAR EXOSKELETON CONTROL SYSTEM BY GAIN SCHEDULING METHOD

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Abstract

The interest in exoskeletons is increasing year by year. There are designed to protect the joints and spine of people, and increases mobility, reduces the load of the musculoskeletal system during long hikes to transport load (backpacks, special equipment, etc.). The technology was used to reduce muscle fatigue and increase human performance. Exoskeletons, as well as any mobile artificial limbs, have control complexities due to nonlinearity and inter-influences between channels.

One of the advanced technologies in this field is an adaptive control, which is an important and interesting area of scientific and industrial researches. The need of adaptive control systems for exoskeletons used in rehabilitation medicine is because exoskeleton's control systems always have some parametric or dynamic uncertainties. There are used to adapt information about the dynamics of the processes to the parameters of PID controllers to ensure stability at all operating points.

The nonlinear control system of the exoskeleton's leg was considered in the work. Using the gain scheduling method, a group of linear PID controllers are designed to ensure the stability of the system at various operating points.

Keywords: exoskeleton, gain scheduling, MATLAB, modeling, multivariable control system, nonlinear systems, PID controller, Simulink.

I. INTRODUCTION

The exoskeletons are designed to expand human functionality, in particular, to improve the life quality of people with disabilities. The exoskeletons are designed to protect the joints and spine of a human. They help to increase the mobility of the human, as well as reduce the load of the musculoskeletal system when transporting long-term heavy load.

The design and production of such devices are related with election of solution of optimal parameters' syntheses issues, design of control systems, transmission mechanisms and software. Our main task is to design an exoskeleton's leg control system, which will allow the most accurate control of the nonlinear model.

To develop a control system, first we need to get a mathematical model of it, do its investigation and then design an appropriate controller.

This work will help to control the exoskeleton's leg of the non-linear system through the gain scheduling method, which will be more effective for exoskeleton control.

II. Materials and method

The Lagrange mechanics are used for modeling of the dynamic systems. Each mechanical system is characterized by a specific function called the Lagrange function and has the following appearance:

$$L(q_1, q_2, \dots, q_s, \dot{q}_1, \dot{q}_2, \dots, \dot{q}_s, t) = L(q, \dot{q}, t), \quad (1)$$

It contains of q and \dot{q} parameters but does not depend on types of derivatives of q .

It is shown that mechanical condition of the system is characterized only by coordinates and velocities. Besides, the Lagrange function has very important feature, when $t = t_1$ and $t = t_2$ moments the system is occupies a position in the space, which is described by q_1 and q_2 coordinates, then its integral is:

$$S = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L(q, \dot{q}, t), \quad (2)$$

which is approaches the lowest possible value. From (2) the equation of the motion is received:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \cdot \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial q} = 0. \tag{3}$$

In the case of a mechanical system with several degrees (s) of freedom, the equation will be:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \cdot \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}_i} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial q_i} = 0, \text{ where } i = (1, 2, \dots, s). \tag{4}$$

If the Lagrange function is known, then the connection among acceleration, velocity, and coordinates can be found out from the equation (4) [1, 2].

To obtain a mathematical model of the system, let's consider a single-legged exoskeleton kinematic scheme:

Fig. 1. This is a sample of a figure caption.

Using the kinematic scheme shown in the Figure 1, it is possible to obtain the coordinates of the points $A(x_1, y_1)$ and $B(x_2, y_2)$ as following:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= l_1 \sin \theta_1, \\ y_1 &= -l_1 \cos \theta_1, \\ x_2 &= l_1 \sin \theta_1 + l_2 \sin \theta_2, \\ y_2 &= -l_1 \cos \theta_1 - l_2 \cos \theta_2, \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where x_1, y_1 and x_2, y_2 accordingly knee and ankle coordinates; θ_1 and θ_2 are the angles of the leg joints with the vertical axis; l_1 and l_2 are the lengths of the leg joints [3,4].

Projections of the linear velocities on the x and y axes can be obtained using the Euler-Lagrange equation:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= f_1(q_1), y_1 = g_1(q_1), \\ x_2 &= f_2(q_2), y_2 = g_2(q_2), \\ q_1 &= \theta_1, q_2 = \theta_2, \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial q_1} \cdot \dot{q}_1 = \frac{\partial(l_1 \sin \theta_1)}{\partial \theta} \cdot \frac{d\theta_1}{dt} = l_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \cos(\theta_1) \\ \dot{y}_1 &= \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial q_1} \cdot \dot{q}_1 = \frac{\partial(-l_1 \cos \theta_1)}{\partial \theta} \cdot \frac{d\theta_1}{dt} = l_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \sin(\theta_1) \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_2 &= \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial q_2} \cdot \dot{q}_2 = \frac{\partial(l_1 \sin \theta_1 + l_2 \sin \theta_2)}{\partial \theta} \cdot \frac{d\theta_2}{dt} = \\ &= l_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \cos(\theta_1) + l_2 \dot{\theta}_2 \cos(\theta_2) \\ \dot{y}_2 &= \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial q_2} \cdot \dot{q}_2 = \frac{\partial(-l_1 \cos \theta_1 - l_2 \cos \theta_2)}{\partial \theta} \cdot \frac{d\theta_2}{dt} = \\ &= l_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \sin(\theta_1) + l_2 \dot{\theta}_2 \sin(\theta_2) \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$\dot{\theta}_1 = \frac{d\theta_1}{dt} = \omega_1, \dot{\theta}_2 = \frac{d\theta_2}{dt} = \omega_2, \tag{9}$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 are the angular velocities.

Thus, the linear velocity will be obtained by the square sum of the velocity projections:

$$\begin{aligned} V_1 &= \sqrt{\dot{x}_1^2 + \dot{y}_1^2} = \\ &= \sqrt{(l_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \cos(\theta_1))^2 + (l_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \sin(\theta_1))^2} = \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sqrt{(l_1 \dot{\theta}_1)^2} = l_1 \dot{\theta}_1, \\
 V_2 &= \sqrt{\dot{x}_2^2 + \dot{y}_2^2} = \\
 &= \sqrt{(l_1 \dot{\theta}_1)^2 + (l_2 \dot{\theta}_2)^2 + 2l_1 l_2 \dot{\theta}_1 \dot{\theta}_2 \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2)}. \tag{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

The Lagrange function is obtained by the difference of kinetic-potential energies:

$$L = T - V \tag{12}$$

where T is the kinetic energy; V is the potential energy.

The kinetic energy equation will be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sum (mV^2) = \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot (m_1 l_1^2 \dot{\theta}_1^2 + m_2 ((l_1 \dot{\theta}_1)^2 + (l_2 \dot{\theta}_2)^2 + \\
 &\quad + 2l_1 l_2 \dot{\theta}_1 \dot{\theta}_2 \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2))). \tag{13}
 \end{aligned}$$

The potential energy equation will be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V &= \sum mgh = m_1 g y_1 + m_2 g y_2 = \\
 &= -(m_1 + m_2) g h_1 \cos(\theta_1) - m_2 g h_2 \cos(\theta_2). \tag{14}
 \end{aligned}$$

So, the Lagrangian function will be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot (m_1 l_1^2 \dot{\theta}_1^2 + m_2 ((l_1 \dot{\theta}_1)^2 + (l_2 \dot{\theta}_2)^2 + \\
 &\quad + 2l_1 l_2 \dot{\theta}_1 \dot{\theta}_2 \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2))) + \\
 &\quad + (m_1 + m_2) g h_1 \cos(\theta_1) + m_2 g h_2 \cos(\theta_2), \tag{15}
 \end{aligned}$$

where m is the mass of the finger and g is the gravitational constant.

The equations of motion will take the following form:

$$\begin{cases} M_1 = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\theta}_1} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta_1} \\ M_2 = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\theta}_2} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta_2} \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_1 &= (m_1 + m_2) l_1 \ddot{\theta}_1 + m_2 l_2 \ddot{\theta}_2 \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + \\
 &\quad + m_2 l_2 \dot{\theta}_2 \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + m_1 + m_2 g \sin(\theta_1), \\
 M_2 &= m_2 l_2 \ddot{\theta}_2 + m_2 l_1 \ddot{\theta}_1 \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2) - \\
 &\quad - m_2 l_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + m_2 g \sin(\theta_2). \tag{17}
 \end{aligned}$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the moments of joints.

The created model in MATLAB/Simulink environment of the nonlinear system of the exoskeleton's leg is represented in Figure 2. The Gain Scheduling method is used for the design of multidimensional automatic control systems (MACS) with similar non-linear interconnections [3, 4]. This method makes it possible to design controllers at different operating points, each of which ensures the stability of the system (Fig. 3) [5].

Fig. 2. The simulation model of the nonlinear system of the mechanical part of the exoskeleton.

To apply the gain scheduling method, it is necessary to linearize the given nonlinear system in the operating points, taking into account the range of movements of the leg during human walking, and then analyze the obtained linear systems. After, PID controllers for each operating points are designed, obtain the dependence of the K_P , K_I , K_D parameters on the system observation parameters, then integrate them into the nonlinear multivariable system [6].

Fig. 3. Block diagram of control system with gain scheduler.

The θ_1 and θ_2 angles formed by the joints of the leg (hip and knee) with a vertical axis were chosen as observation parameters. Their ranges can be determined in case when during walking knee and hip angles vary accordingly $[0: \pi/3]$ and $[-\pi/6: \pi/6]$ radians. Based on the obtained ranges was performed linearization of the nonlinear system at 441 operating points. The obtained liner systems were analyzed. The step response curves of the closed loop systems are observed in the Fig. 4, 5, which indicate that it is necessary to design controllers for system stabilization [7,8].

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} q_{11} & q_{12} \\ q_{21} & q_{22} \end{pmatrix}. \tag{18}$$

MATLAB/Simulink environment is shown in Fig. 6 and in Fig.7, where box with dotted lines indicates the mechanical part of the exoskeleton leg [9], which is shown in Figure 2. In the block diagram q_{11}, q_{12}, q_{21} and q_{22} are interrelationships which can be represented by the matrix Q:

Fig. 4. The step responses of θ_1 closed-loop control system.

Fig. 5. The step responses of θ_2 closed-loop control system.

The block diagram and model of a nonlinear system with PID controllers designed by using gain scheduling method in

Fig. 6. Exoskeleton leg Simulink model with PID controllers designed by using gain scheduling method.

Fig. 7. Block diagram of the exoskeleton leg control system.

Designed a PID controller for one operating point and used in 441 operating points and their step response curves were extracted (Fig. 8). From the received curves, it can be seen that the system exhibits different stabilization parameters at different operating points, which need to be corrected by designing separate PID regulators for each operating point [10,11]. As a result, the PID regulator was designed for each with the same stability parameters ($\delta = 2.34\%$, $t_r = 0.0005\text{sec}$., $t_s = 0.004\text{sec}$.). The step response curves of which are shown in Fig. 9.

PID controller K_P , K_I , K_D parameters dependence from θ_1 and θ_2 observation parameters derived in the Figure 10, 11, 12 - hip joint dependencies, Figure 13, 14, 15 - knee joint dependencies). This shows how the PID controller parameters should be changed at different working angles (operating points).

Fig. 8. Linearized system step responses without gain scheduler.

Fig. 9. Linearized system step responses with gain scheduler.

Fig. 10. Hip PID controller K_p dependence from θ_1 and θ_2 observation parameters.

Fig. 11. Hip PID controller K_i dependence from θ_1 and θ_2 observation parameters.

Fig. 12. Hip PID controller K_d dependence from θ_1 and θ_2 observation parameters.

Fig. 13. Knee PID controller K_p dependence from θ_1 and θ_2 observation parameters.

Fig. 14. Knee PID controller K_I dependence from θ_1 and θ_2 observation parameters.

Fig. 15. Knee PID controller K_D dependence from θ_1 and θ_2 observation parameters.

RESULTS

As a result of the human gait algorithm which used for the designed exoskeleton, the coincidence of the input-output signals becomes apparent (Fig. 16). A human gait algorithm was given to the system input to test the obtained method. In the Figure 16, the desired angles of the hip and knee joints are shown in red and blue lines, respectively, and the output angles are shown in dotted lines. The results show that the input and output angles correspond.

Fig. 16. Hip PID controller K_D dependence from θ_1 and θ_2 observation parameters.

CONCLUSION

This paper presents the mathematical model and design features of the control system of the exoskeleton's leg. The nonlinear model of the exoskeleton's leg is developed and investigated. The open and close loop systems have been developed and analyzed. For the system stabilization, the PID controllers are developed by using the gain scheduling method in 441 operating points. It is concluded that the gain scheduling method results are satisfied the necessary requirements for use in the exoskeleton control system.

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References

1. D. Morin, "Introduction to classical mechanics", Cambridge University, UK, 710 p., 2008.
2. Z. Khanamiryan, A. Mkhitarian, "Modeling and Analysis of the Prosthetic Bionic Hand Control System", 2020 IEEE International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Photonics (EExPolytech), St. Petersburg, Russia, 2020.
3. Chen Li-jie, "Research on the nonlinear dynamical behavior of double pendulum", Jilin, China, 2011 International Conference on Mechatronic Science, Electric Engineering and Computer (MEC).
4. A. V. Borisov & G. M. Rozenblat, Modeling the Dynamics of an Exoskeleton with Control Torques in the Joints and a Variable Length of the Links Using the Recurrent Method for Constructing Differential Equations of Motion, Journal of Computer and Systems Sciences International volume 57, 2018, pp. 319–347
5. Maryam Khamar, Mehdi Edrisi, Mohsen Zahiri, Human-exoskeleton control simulation, kinetic and kinematic modeling and parameters extraction, MethodsX Volume 6, 2019, pp. 1838-1846
6. Norman S. Nise, Control Systems Engineering, book, Wiley 6 edition, 2010, 944p.
7. J.S. Shamma; M. Athans, Gain scheduling: potential hazards and possible remedies, IEEE Control Systems Magazine Volume 12, Issue 3, June 1992, pp. 101-107
8. D. Rotondo, Advances in Gain-Scheduling and Fault Tolerant Control Techniques, 2018, 255p.

9. L. Miková, I. Virgala, and M. Kelemen, "Speed control of DC motor" American Journal of Mechanical Engineering, USA, Vol. 4, No. 7, pp. 380-384, 2016

10. Lin Liu, Steffen Leonhardt, Berno J.E. Mischel, Experimental Validation of a Torque-Controlled Variable Stiffness Actuator Tuned by Gain Scheduling,

IEEE/ASME TRANSACTIONS ON MECHATRONICS, 2018

11. L. Liu, Zejun Hong, Bernhard Penzlin, Low Impedance-Guaranteed Gain-Scheduled GESO for Torque-Controlled VSA, with Application of Exoskeleton-Assisted Sit-to-Stand, IEEE/ASME TRANSACTIONS ON MECHATRONICS, 2020.

ТЕПЛОВОЙ РАСЧЕТ СОЛНЕЧНОГО КОЛЛЕКТОРА И ЕГО ТЕХНИКО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ

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